

Argeş County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance
Centrul Judeţean de Resurse şi Asistenţă Educaţională Argeş

AsProEdu Association
Asociaţia AsProEdu

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Ars Libri
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Argeş County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance
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SECTION A

Education

Moderator: Mrs. Camelia IOANĂȘ

Argeș County Center for Resources and Educational Assistance

THE SCHOOL'S OPERATING CULTURE CREATES THE BASIS FOR COOPERATION BETWEEN HOME AND SCHOOL

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Abstract. Cooperation between home and school is important from the first day of school. Cooperation between home and school should be structured as a continuum, in which cooperation can have different tasks and forms in different phases. The starting point for home and school cooperation is a good, safe everyday life for the student and support for learning goals and study motivation.

Pupils' guardians are offered opportunities to get to know and participate in the everyday life of the school, the planning and development of the goals of the school's operations and educational work, together with the entire school's staff and pupils. A common reflection on values creates a basis for joint educational work. An open and interactive operating culture and the experience of belonging to the school community are important in the cooperation between home and school and promote shared responsibility education. (Finnish National Agency of Education)

Parents have primary responsibility for their child's upbringing. Teachers, managers and principals cooperate with guardians while supporting guardians in their important educational work. (OAJ, teachers trade union)

Cooperation between home and school requires leadership. The principal plays a key role in the planning and implementation of cooperation with the homes. Although each school and teacher cooperate between home and school in their own way, the methods of operation must be sufficiently uniform. The school's operating culture has a significant impact on how parents' involvement and home-school cooperation in the school's everyday life takes shape. When parents are involved in strengthening well-being in the school community, they commit to supporting the school's goals and activities and valuing the school.

Well-functioning communication is an important part of the cooperation between home and school. Parents' evenings are still a common way to cooperate between home and school. Parents' evenings should be interactive, conversational or functional. From the parents' point of view, it is important to be able to regularly discuss their child and the child's schooling with the teacher. Parents can support the well-being of the class and the entire school community in many ways and strengthen the sense of community.

Equality in home-school cooperation means the opportunity for all students' parents to participate and be involved in their child's schooling and in home-school cooperation. Let's make a common action plan what help our school collaborate together with parents. (Finnish Parents Union)

EUROPEAN EDUCATIONAL SUPPORT SERVICES

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Abstract. This study examines the role of European educational support services in the context of Portugal, focusing on how these services are implemented and their effectiveness in supporting students within the national education system. Educational support services in Portugal are integral in addressing various challenges, including language barriers, socio-economic inequalities, and integration of students with special needs. The European Union's role in facilitating these services includes funding programs, providing frameworks for inclusion, and promoting educational mobility across member states. The Portuguese case highlights the integration of EU-driven initiatives such as Erasmus+ and the European Social Fund in improving access to education, enhancing teaching quality, and promoting lifelong learning. This paper discusses the impact of these services on students' academic outcomes, their role in fostering equality, and how Portugal aligns with broader EU educational policies. It also explores the future challenges and opportunities for improving educational support services in Portugal, particularly in the post-pandemic era.

Objectives. The paper presents the case study of Portugal laying emphasis on: the inclusion of students with special needs, educational and career counseling, inclusive education, academic mobility, educational support services, challenges and opportunities, digital education and lifelong learning, educational support for emigrants and refugees.

Results. European Educational Support Services have significantly improved access to education for marginalized and disadvantaged groups in Portugal. Initiatives such as the Erasmus+ program and the European Social Fund have helped reduce barriers such as financial constraints, enabling more students from low-income families to attend higher education institutions. Mobility programs also promote the internationalization of higher education in Portugal, helping to elevate the global competitiveness of Portuguese universities. European funding has supported the professional development of teachers in Portugal, improving the overall quality of education. Specialized programs have trained educators in innovative teaching methods, particularly in the areas of digital literacy and inclusion. The study highlighted that EU educational policies and support services have bolstered the lifelong learning agenda in Portugal. Programs funded by the European Union have helped adults, particularly those with lower levels of education, access training and re-skilling opportunities. European support services have helped integrate students with special educational needs (SEN) in Portuguese schools. EU-driven initiatives have provided funding for the development of inclusive education programs and training for teachers to better support these students.

Conclusions. The educational system in Portugal is structured to provide a comprehensive, equitable, and quality education for its citizens, with significant reforms over the years to modernize and align with European Union standards.

Keywords: inclusion, special needs, inclusive education, mobility, lifelong learning.

THE MOTIVATION OF THE MOTIVATORS

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Abstract. Motivation, self-trust, and consciousness are interconnected psychological constructs that play a vital role in personal development, goal attainment, and mental well-being. Motivation serves as the driving force behind human action, encompassing both intrinsic and extrinsic factors that inspire individuals to pursue their objectives. Self-trust is the foundation of confidence and resilience, enabling individuals to rely on their abilities, make sound decisions, and navigate challenges with assurance. Consciousness, particularly in the form of self-awareness and mindfulness, fosters a deep understanding of one's thoughts, emotions, and values, aligning actions with authentic intentions. Together, these constructs create a synergistic relationship where consciousness enhances self-trust, self-trust amplifies motivation, and motivation drives purposeful action. Cultivating these qualities involves intentional practices such as goal setting, positive self-reflection, and mindfulness exercises, contributing to holistic growth and sustained well-being. This abstract highlights their interplay, underscoring their significance in achieving personal and professional fulfilment.

Objectives. Inspire the audience, clarify the concept of motivation, highlight the importance of motivation, provide practical strategies, empower self-belief, address common barriers, use real-life examples, create a call to action.

Results. The speech has the following outcomes: Participants develop a clearer understanding of what drives their motivation and how to sustain it over time. Attendees gain clarity on setting Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound goals. Listeners become more aware of the importance of patience in achieving long-term success. Greater self-awareness among participants, enabling them to recognize their strengths, weaknesses, and emotional triggers. Audience members are better equipped to align their actions with their values and maintain a sense of purpose. Attendees leave the speech with actionable insights and tools to incorporate motivation, SMART goals, patience, empathy, and self-consciousness into their daily lives. Immediate steps are taken to apply these concepts, such as setting new goals, practicing mindfulness, or improving communication with others. Enhanced ability to navigate challenges with a positive mindset and emotional control. Strengthened connections between personal growth and the broader impact on relationships and society.

Conclusions. By addressing these key areas, the speech fosters a holistic approach to self-improvement, equipping individuals with the mindset and tools to succeed in various aspects of life.

Keywords: motivation, SMART goals, empathy, self-consciousness.

TECHNOLOGY IN THE CLASSROOM (TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION)

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Abstract. The integration of technology into the classroom has revolutionized the way education is delivered, enhancing both teaching and learning experiences. This study explores the impact of technology integration on student engagement, academic performance, and overall classroom dynamics. It examines how digital tools, such as smartboards, tablets, and online platforms, facilitate interactive learning, support diverse learning styles, and provide access to a vast range of educational resources. The research highlights the benefits of technology in promoting collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity among students, while also addressing challenges such as the digital divide, screen time concerns, and the need for teacher training. The study concludes that when effectively integrated, technology can create a more personalized, engaging, and efficient learning environment, preparing students for success in an increasingly digital world.

Objectives. The objectives aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of how technology can be leveraged to improve educational outcomes and support both teaching and learning in the modern classroom.

Methods. Desk research.

Results. The paper presents the benefits of technology integration in the classroom: enhanced student engagement, personalized learning, improved access to educational resources, fostering collaboration and communication, development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, Improved Teacher Instructional Methods, Increased Efficiency and Organization, Facilitation of Remote Learning and Flexibility, Encouragement of Digital Literacy, Preparation for the Future Workforce, Real-Time Feedback and Assessment, Enhanced Creativity and Innovation.

Conclusions. The integration of technology into the classroom offers numerous benefits for both students and teachers. It enhances engagement, personalizes learning, promotes collaboration, and equips students with the skills they need for future success. When implemented effectively, technology creates a dynamic and efficient learning environment that fosters academic growth, critical thinking, and creativity, while preparing students for the demands of the digital age.

Keywords: technology, classroom, learning environment.

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS

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Abstract. Interactive teaching methods engage students actively in the learning process, encouraging participation, collaboration, and critical thinking. Incorporating interactive teaching methods transforms the classroom into a vibrant learning community, fostering not only academic success but also essential life skills. These methods create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment, helping students to retain information better and develop essential life skills.

Objectives. The paper aims at presenting the most frequently used interactive methods in the classroom: problem-based learning (PBL), project-based, role-playing, guided discussions, brainstorming, collaborative learning, debates, educational games, gallery walk, discovery learning, think-pair-share, flipped classroom, case studies, peer teaching, interactive simulations.

Methods. Desk research, case studies.

Results. Interactive teaching methods are vital for creating an engaging and effective learning environment. Here are some key reasons highlighting their importance: enhanced engagement, improved retention and understanding, development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, enhanced communication and collaboration, adaptability to different learning styles, increased student responsibility and autonomy, immediate feedback and assessment, promotes creativity and innovation, builds social and emotional skills, real-world application, boosts confidence and self-esteem, fosters a positive learning environment

Conclusions. Interactive teaching methods are pivotal in modern education, as they foster a dynamic and engaging learning environment. By actively involving students in the learning process, these methods enhance understanding, retention, and application of knowledge. They encourage critical thinking, collaboration, and communication, which are essential skills in the 21st century. Interactive techniques, such as group discussions, problem-solving activities, and technology integration, cater to diverse learning styles and promote deeper comprehension. Ultimately, the adoption of interactive teaching methods transforms the classroom into an inclusive space where students are motivated to participate, leading to improved academic outcomes and personal growth.

Keywords: interactive, teaching method, learning environment.

PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN BY IDENTIFYING COMPETENCY AREAS IN NEED OF REMEDIAL SUPPORT

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Abstract. In this article, we begin by defining the term “school competency” and outlining the steps involved in achieving the desired outcomes. School competencies are related to the graduate’s training profile—in our case, the profile of a middle school graduate. Among these competencies, we focus on communication skills in the mother tongue and mathematical competencies, as these are the only ones assessed through an exam at the end of the study cycle.

Objectives. Identifying areas of competency that require remedial support in schools is a crucial process for helping students reach their full potential.

Methods. We will present several effective strategies for identifying these areas: formative and summative assessments, student self-evaluation questionnaires, teacher feedback, parent-teacher meetings, diagnostic tests with itemized analysis of results, classroom observation, standardized tests, progress in assignments and projects, identification of learning styles, and monitoring of study time. All of these strategies will be analyzed both in terms of their specific characteristics and the benefits they provide. Furthermore, we will propose remedial measures and our strategy for implementing these measures to achieve the expected results (SMART objectives).

Results. Improving student’s skills by applying remedial measures.

Conclusions. Providing the right support and resources to learn contributes to cognitive development, one of the key aspects of children’s personal development.

Keywords: competency, analysis, objective, remediation

THE ROLE OF PROTECTIVE FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESILIENCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. The concept of resilience is essentially defined as the set of skills that the individual puts into practice in order to resist a problematic context, or even to take advantage of it, by creating defense mechanisms that protect him all the time throughout his life. At the base of any resilience mechanism there are protective factors and vulnerability factors, both of which can be external and internal. In the case of children and adolescents, the presence of a "resilience tutor" plays a very important role and adults must be aware of this status and offer support to adolescents at risk. This support can take various forms, from simple presence with the child / adolescent in the difficult situation to the creation of contexts for learning resilience.

As an adaptive mechanism, resilience can manifest itself at a certain moment, that is to say in the short term, or it can be constituted as a process which becomes in some way permanent. To reach this point, the adolescent must metallize the difficult situation he is faced with (give meaning to it) and develop it from a psychological point of view in order to integrate it as adaptive behavior.

Objectives. Defining resilience. Presenting methods to cultivate resilience.

Methods. Desk research.

Results. Stimulating resilience on an intrapsychic level means trying to change the adolescent's modes of adaptation, thus acting on defense mechanisms, a process which targets the very foundations of an individual's personality.

However, behaving in a resilient way in a certain moment of life does not indicate that the young person will be able to demonstrate such behavior forever and in the face of everything.

Being resilient therefore does not mean being invincible or invulnerable (in essence, we are all sensitive beings who act and react), resilient behavior being rather a flexible attitude of adaptation to contexts which may pose problems.

Conclusions. How to cultivate resilience? The protective and risk factors, in their dynamics, build the great mechanism of resilience, defined as the capacity of the individual (in our case of the young person) to overcome adversity.

Keywords: resilience, vulnerability, protection.

SELF-KNOWLEDGE AND SELF-DETERMINATION- A SYLLABUS OFER FOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The learning motivation represents the triggering factor of the desire for knowledge, this leading to the development of students' skills. The current study enhances a series of concepts, these being approached through a holistic and systematic manner, by using an optional subject curriculum for high school students, students that have both cognitive abilities and also a bare minimum of knowledge which allows them to comprehend and facilitate them an insightful meaning, therefore leading to personal growth. Self-knowledge contributes to strengthening the Self and to self-regulation. Once these goals have been achieved, we therefore admit that the desire for learning has been naturally framed, and as a consequence, it leads to the search for answers in order to avoid uncertainty, triggering the motivation for study which plays an important part among the Educational science researchers' concerns. Self-knowledge during adolescence occupies an important place among students' concerns, a program aimed at self-knowledge can answer many questions related to the uncertainties faced by the adolescent student. We also consider the didactic strategies used in personal development activities (games, psychological tests, creative expressive techniques) to be easy, appreciated by the students and thus through such classes the student discovers the pleasure of being present during the course hours.

Objectives. The purpose of this work is to demonstrate empirically the effectiveness of the implementation of an optional educational discipline that allows high school students to discover the need for autonomy, competence and relationship by capitalizing on expressive-creative techniques.

Methods. Desk research.

Conclusions. Students' access to information in modern society is facilitated by modern technology and more, and student interest decreases during class time. Also, the development of skills has far exceeded the assimilation of information, in this sense we believe that with this change it is imperative to make changes in school programs as well. Over time, didactic strategies have been revolutionized, through the development of modern teaching aids, a wide range of active-participative methods and modern techniques, but despite all this, the motivation of students is decreasing. We believe that the concepts listed through this article can be operationalized within an optional curriculum, their range being wide for high school students. The limits of this study are given by the non-existence of such programs developed over long periods of time, a longitudinal study being able to highlight the advantages of their application on the personal development of young people who have followed such programs.

Key words: students, skills, optional discipline, motivation for learning, self-knowledge

MOTIVATION AND CONFLICT IN THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. In the school environment, motivation and conflict are crucial factors that influence the development of students, the dynamics of relationships between them and the educational process. Understanding these concepts can help create a harmonious environment and optimize educational outcomes. School motivation is the force that drives students to learn, being of two types: internal and external. School conflict can be internal (struggle with oneself) or external (between students, student-teacher, student-parents). Motivation is the internal or external energy that drives students to actively participate in the learning process.

Types of motivation: Internal: The desire to learn out of curiosity, passion, or personal enjoyment (e.g., a student who studies science because they enjoy understanding natural phenomena), External: External factors such as rewards, grades, parental pressure, or social recognition. Strong motivation, especially internal motivation, increases academic performance and students' resilience in the face of difficulties.

School conflict refers to tensions or confrontations that arise between students, between students and teachers, or between other parties involved in the educational community.

Types of conflict: Internal: The student struggles with his or her own anxiety, lack of confidence, or emotional conflicts, External: Between students: bullying, competition for results, differences of opinion, Student-teacher: Mismatch of communication styles or lack of empathy, Student-parent: Too high expectations or pressure to perform. Impact of conflict: If not managed, conflict can lead to decreased academic performance, withdrawal of students from social activities and impaired mental health.

Motivation and conflict can interact strongly in the school environment.

Conclusions. Motivation and conflict are interconnected and strongly influence students' development in the school environment. Careful management of these factors contributes to the development of a healthy educational environment in which students can learn and grow harmoniously.

Keywords: internal motivation, external motivation, school conflict, mediation, active learning.

MOTIVATION AND CONFLICT IN THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT

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EFFECTIVE CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. Conflicts are an inevitable part of the educational environment, arising between teachers, students, parents or even within the educational team. This article explores the importance of identifying the causes, developing communication skills and using mediation strategies to create a climate of collaboration and respect in schools.

Educational conflict management is essential for ensuring a harmonious and productive environment in educational institutions. A properly managed conflict can become an opportunity for growth, but if ignored, it can generate major tensions.

Results. Common causes of conflicts in education: Differences in perspective – Differing values and expectations between teachers, students and parents, Lack of communication – Misunderstandings or incomplete information often lead to tensions, Stress and Overload – Pressure on teachers and students can amplify conflicts. Effective Management Strategies: Active Listening – Encouraging the parties involved to express their points of view clearly, Empathy – Creating a safe space for understanding the emotions of each party, Mediation Techniques – Using a mediator to find mutually accepted solutions, Clear Rules of Conduct – Establishing common norms and expectations in the school community. The Role of Teachers in Conflict Resolution: Teachers must be models of conflict management, demonstrating calm, patience and respect. Continuing professional development in the field of conflict management can significantly contribute to their effectiveness.

Conclusions. Managing educational conflicts should not be seen as an insurmountable challenge, but as an opportunity to improve interpersonal relationships and the school atmosphere. Through open communication, empathy, and collaboration, any conflict can become a positive experience for all parties involved.

Keywords: educational conflict, communication, mediation, collaboration, resolution strategies.

COMMUNICATION AND SCHOOL CONFLICT: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. Conflicts in the school environment are inevitable, given the diversity of students' personalities, interests and values. At their core is communication, which can become both an effective solution and a factor that amplifies tensions. Understanding the methods of managing these conflicts through effective communication is essential for creating a balanced educational environment. Although frequent, conflicts can be successfully addressed through open and assertive dialogue. Resolution strategies include mediation, developing emotional intelligence and practicing active listening. Promoting a climate based on respect and communication contributes significantly to preventing and resolving tensions, thus supporting a harmonious school environment.

Types of School Conflict. Conflicts in schools can range from minor ones, such as disagreements between classmates, to more serious situations, such as bullying. These can involve students, teachers, or even parents. Often, a lack of effective communication leads to the escalation of problems.

The role of communication in preventing conflicts. Open and assertive communication is essential for preventing conflicts. Teachers can promote active dialogue, encouraging students to express their points of view without fear of being judged. Also, creating clear rules of interaction helps establish a climate of mutual respect.

Conflict management strategies

- 1. Mediation:** A neutral mediator, such as a teacher or counselor, can help the parties involved find common solutions.
- 2. Emotional education:** Students should be taught to manage their emotions and communicate calmly in tense situations.
- 3. Active listening:** Actively engaging in listening to the perspectives of others reduces tensions and fosters empathy.

Conclusions. Effective communication is key to reducing conflict in the school environment. By promoting a climate of respect and open dialogue, schools can become safe spaces for student development. The active involvement of teachers, counselors, and parents is essential in this process.

Keywords: school conflict, communication, mediation, prevention, emotional education, active listening, respect, dialogue.

SECTION B

Psychology

Moderator: Mrs. Camelia IOANĂȘ

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THE PSYCHOLOGY OF SOCIAL NETWORKS

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Abstract. This study explores the psychological dynamics of social networks, focusing on their impact on individual behaviour, mental health, and social interactions. Social networks have become integral to modern communication, influencing how people perceive themselves and others. The research examines key psychological aspects, such as the effects of social comparison, the influence of online interactions on self-esteem, and the role of social media in shaping identity. Additionally, it investigates the relationship between social network usage and mental health outcomes, including anxiety, depression, and loneliness. The study highlights both positive effects, like increased social support and connectivity, and negative consequences, such as cyberbullying and addiction. Through surveys, experiments, and data analysis, this research provides insights into how social networks affect psychological well-being and offers recommendations for promoting healthier online behaviors.

Objectives. The main objectives are: examine the impact of social networks on mental health, investigate the role of social comparison, assess the influence of online interactions on identity formation, understand the effects of social networks on interpersonal relationships, explore the role of social networks in social support, analyze the relationship between social media usage patterns and addiction, identify strategies for healthy social media usage.

Methods. Interview

Results. High usage of social networks is correlated with increased levels of anxiety, depression, and loneliness, particularly among younger users. However, moderate and mindful use can enhance well-being by providing social support and reducing feelings of isolation. Frequent social comparison on platforms like Instagram and Facebook often leads to decreased self-esteem and life satisfaction. Social networks serve as significant spaces for identity exploration, especially for adolescents and young adults. While social networks facilitate the maintenance of long-distance relationships and provide a platform for reconnecting with old friends, they can also lead to superficial connections and reduced quality in face-to-face interactions. Online communities often offer users a sense of belonging and shared experience. Excessive social media usage (more than 3 hours per day) is linked to addictive behaviors, such as compulsive checking of notifications and difficulty in reducing usage.

Conclusions. The results highlight the complex psychological effects of social networks, indicating both potential benefits and risks, and emphasizing the importance of balanced usage for mental well-being.

Keywords: social networks, mental health, social interactions.

MINDFULNESS FOR REDUCING ANXIETY IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract. Mindfulness has become an increasingly popular and effective tool for helping students manage anxiety in schools. Mindfulness involves paying focused, non-judgmental attention to the present moment, which can help reduce stress and promote emotional well-being. This practice is particularly beneficial in school settings, where students face academic pressures, social challenges, and personal stressors that can contribute to anxiety.

Objectives. Presenting the key concepts of mindfulness for anxiety that can be used in schools: awareness of the present moment, non-judgmental awareness, breathing techniques, grounding techniques, self-compassion.

Methods. Desk research, case studies.

Results. The research found that some benefits of mindfulness for anxiety in schools are: reduces stress and anxiety: research shows that mindfulness can significantly reduce feelings of anxiety and stress by allowing students to better regulate their emotional responses, improves concentration and focus, mindfulness practices help students improve their attention and focus, reducing the negative impact of anxiety on their ability to concentrate in class, enhances emotional regulation, improves self-esteem, by practicing mindfulness, students become more accepting of themselves, which can lead to increased self-esteem and a more positive outlook on their abilities. Also, the challenges that may appear are: time constraints, one of the challenges of implementing mindfulness in schools is the time commitment, schools often have tight schedules, and finding time for mindfulness practice may be difficult, resistance to mindfulness, some students or educators may be skeptical about mindfulness practices or may not fully understand their potential benefits, education and gradual integration are key to overcoming this barrier, cultural sensitivity, mindfulness programs should be adapted to the cultural and demographic needs of students. It is important to ensure that mindfulness practices are inclusive and resonate with diverse student populations, sustaining practice, like any skill, mindfulness requires consistent practice to be effective. Schools may need to offer ongoing support and resources to ensure that students continue to benefit from mindfulness techniques.

Conclusions. Mindfulness is a powerful tool for helping students manage anxiety in schools. By fostering emotional regulation, reducing stress, and enhancing self-awareness, mindfulness empowers students to handle the pressures they face in a more balanced and focused manner. When implemented thoughtfully, mindfulness can create a more supportive and mentally healthy school environment, benefiting both students and educators.

Keywords: mindfulness, anxiety, attention, tool.

THE IMPACT OF STRESS ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Abstract. Stress is a common experience among students and can significantly affect academic performance. This study examines the relationship between stress and academic achievement, focusing on how both chronic and acute stressors influence cognitive functions, emotional well-being, and overall academic outcomes. The research highlights various sources of stress in the academic environment, including academic pressure, time management challenges, and social factors. It explores how stress can impair concentration, memory retention, and problem-solving abilities, leading to decreased performance. Additionally, the study investigates coping mechanisms students use to manage stress and the effectiveness of stress reduction techniques.

Objectives: examine the sources of stress among students, analyze the effect of stress on cognitive functions, explore the relationship between stress levels and academic achievement, identify the psychological and emotional effects of stress, evaluate coping mechanisms and stress management strategies, examine the role of social and environmental factors, assess the impact of chronic vs. acute stress, explore gender and demographic differences in stress responses, provide recommendations for stress reduction interventions.

Methods. Interview.

Results. Students reported that high expectations from teachers and parents were linked to increased anxiety about performance, while balancing academics with extracurricular activities further exacerbated stress. Stress was found to significantly affect students' mental health, leading to increased anxiety, depression, and burnout. Effective time management emerged as one of the most common and successful coping strategies for reducing stress, particularly for students who engaged in planning and prioritizing tasks. Social support from friends, family, and peers was also found to be an important factor in managing stress. The study found some gender differences in how stress was experienced. Female students reported higher levels of anxiety and emotional distress, while male students were less likely to report emotional effects and more likely to use avoidance strategies like withdrawing from schoolwork. Age and year level also played a role, with older students reporting higher levels of stress.

Conclusions. The results of the study highlight that stress significantly affects students' academic performance, with both cognitive and emotional consequences. The findings underscore the importance of developing coping strategies, increasing awareness of stress management techniques, and creating supportive academic environments to help students mitigate the adverse effects of stress on their academic success.

Keywords: stress, academic performance, anxiety, performance.

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN COMMUNICATION STYLES

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Abstract. This study explores the distinct communication styles typically exhibited by men and women, examining both verbal and nonverbal behaviors. It highlights how gender influences communication patterns, such as women's tendency towards expressive and relational language and men's preference for assertive and informational communication. The research delves into differences in listening styles, conflict resolution approaches, as well as the impact of these differences on interpersonal and professional relationships.

Objectives. Main objectives: examine verbal/ nonverbal communication patterns, understand listening styles, analyze conflict resolution approaches, investigate the use of humor, identify topic preferences in communication, assess communication goals.

Methods. Observation, case study.

Results. Women were found to use more expressive and relational language, often focusing on emotions, empathy, and building connections. Men, in contrast, tend to use more assertive, direct language, often focusing on facts, information, and establishing their authority. Women exhibited more expressive nonverbal communication, including facial expressions, gestures, and frequent eye contact, which served to reinforce empathy and connection. Men displayed more neutral or reserved nonverbal cues, with less emphasis on facial expression and more focused on maintaining dominance through posture, limited eye contact, or using space. Women were found to be more active listeners, while men, still attentive listeners, were generally more focused on problem-solving and less likely to use nonverbal cues to show active listening. Women preferred collaborative and compromise-oriented approaches to resolving conflicts, seeking to preserve relationships and avoid direct confrontation. Men were more likely to adopt a competitive or solution-focused approach, prioritizing problem-solving and efficiency over relational aspects of the conflict. Gender differences in communication were found to impact relationship dynamics, with misunderstandings arising when one gender's style was not recognized or respected by the other.

Conclusions. The paper aims at providing a comprehensive understanding of how gender influences communication styles and the implications for effective interaction. These results demonstrate that while gender differences in communication styles are evident, there is significant overlap, and individuals may display behaviors that do not strictly adhere to traditional gender norms. Recognizing these differences and fostering adaptive communication skills can improve interpersonal interactions in both personal and professional settings.

Keywords: Communication style, gender differences, listening styles.

DIMENSIONS OF THE FAMILY ENVIRONMENT AND COPING MECHANISMS IN ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract. The relationship between **family environment** and **coping mechanisms** in adolescents is crucial for understanding adolescent development, emotional health, and resilience.

The family environment plays a key role in shaping an adolescent's psychological, emotional, and social development. Several dimensions of the family environment can affect how adolescents cope with stress: **emotional support, cohesion and bonding, conflict and tension, parental control and discipline.**

Objectives. The present research, aims at investigating the relationship between family environment factors and the coping strategies of adolescents, by separately evaluating family environmental factors within households where adolescents live and their developed coping strategies.

Methods. Two questionnaires were applied, one regarding the dimensions of the family environment (Family of Origin Questionnaire, by A. J. Hovestadt, W. T. Anderson, F. P. Piercy, S. W. Cochran and M. Fine) and the second regarding coping strategies (CERQ - Evaluation Questionnaire of cognitive emotional coping, by Garnefski, Kraaij and Spinhoven, 2001).

Results. 57 teenagers, aged 17 to 19, participated in the research from an educational unit in Piteşti. There is a statistically significant relationship between the family environment factors: *clarity of expression, responsibility, openness, creating a warm atmosphere in the house mood and tone, respect for others* and the coping strategy *positive refocusing, catastrophizing coping strategy, acceptance, refocusing on planning, blaming others.*

Conclusions. It is the family environment that imprints on the adolescent's behaviour certain particularities of behavior.

Keywords: family environment factors, copying strategy, adolescents.

CASE STUDY: A.P. – FROM A SAD CASE OF EMOTIONAL ABUSE TO AN EMPOWERING STORY SERVING AS A SOURCE OF INSPIRATION FOR OTHERS

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Abstract. The paper depicts the story of an adolescent, the turmoil of a young woman who went through emotional abuse, who despite all the trauma she has endured eventually finds the confidence that things will one day get better. Although the past still casts a shadow over her days, her courage to open up to a therapist about her suffering brings relief and hope for healing.

Her strength stems from the love she has for her little brother whom she raises the way she would have needed to be raised as a little girl.

Her story mirrors a society that seems to turn a blind eye to abuse and sorrow.

Objectives. The paper aims at encouraging people, regardless of their age to express their emotions and mold the negative ones towards growth. Therefore, courage is key when facing abuse no matter what kind. Another objective is to pinpoint the ruthlessness of society and how much help the support of others could bring to the drama some children face without even showing it.

Methods and materials. Projective tests and guided imagery therapy

Results. The young girl has recovered faith in the process, in herself and other people that might help her overcome the trauma.

Conclusions. Her case is now an example of courage that helps others to share one's debilitating experiences and seek professional help.

Keywords: Emotional abuse, trauma, counseling

FOREVER TOGETHER

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Abstract. This study explores the transformative journey of a mother who, after the tragic loss of her child, embarks on a path to better understand children and their developmental needs by pursuing a career in education. Driven by a profound desire to channel her grief into meaningful change, she immerses herself in the study of child psychology and pedagogy. Her journey highlights the healing power of education and the resilience of the human spirit. This narrative delves into the intersections of personal loss, emotional growth, and professional development, illustrating how personal tragedy can inspire a profound commitment to nurturing and educating future generations.

Objectives. To explore the impact of personal loss on career transformation and motivation in education, to assess the effectiveness of studying child psychology and pedagogy in helping individuals reconnect with their purpose and contribute meaningfully to society, to understand the psychological journey of a mother dealing with the loss of a child and how it informs her approach to child development and teaching, to investigate the role of education as a therapeutic tool in coping with grief and personal tragedy, to examine how personal experiences of loss can influence teaching philosophies and practices, to contribute to the broader understanding of how personal adversity can lead to positive outcomes in professional and personal development.

Methods. Case study.

Results. Engaging in the study of child psychology and pedagogy provides a therapeutic pathway for coping with grief, allowing individuals to channel their emotions into constructive and meaningful pursuits. Personal experiences with loss enrich the teacher's empathy and understanding of children's emotional and developmental needs, fostering a nurturing and supportive learning environment. The journey from personal tragedy to professional dedication illustrates the resilience of the human spirit and underscores the potential for personal adversity to inspire significant contributions to society. The unique perspective gained from personal loss can shape innovative and compassionate teaching practices, benefiting both the educator and their students by creating a more inclusive and empathetic classroom. This narrative highlights the importance of integrating personal experiences into professional roles, encouraging educational communities to support and value diverse life experiences in shaping effective teaching methodologies.

Conclusions. The experience of profound personal loss can serve as a powerful motivator for career transformation, leading individuals to seek deeper understanding and purpose through education and teaching.

Keywords: journey, career transformation, growth, understanding.

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL COUNSELING PROCESS

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Abstract. The psychological counseling process is a structured, client-centered approach aimed at promoting mental health and well-being. This process involves several stages, including assessment, goal setting, intervention, and evaluation. During the initial phase, counselors gather detailed information to understand the client's concerns, history, and psychological state. The goal-setting stage focuses on collaboratively defining achievable outcomes tailored to the client's needs. Intervention strategies are then implemented, utilizing evidence-based techniques such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, psychodynamic approaches, or other therapeutic modalities. The process concludes with an evaluation phase, where progress is reviewed, and further steps are planned to ensure sustained improvement. The counseling process emphasizes confidentiality, empathy, and a supportive environment, facilitating personal growth and resilience in clients.

Objectives. To assess the effectiveness of various counseling techniques and interventions based on existing research findings and case studies, to identify current trends, emerging issues and challenges in the field of psychological counseling, including technological advancements, cultural considerations, and access to services, to compile best practices and recommendations for improving the counseling process, ensuring it is client-centered, culturally sensitive, and evidence-based, to provide insights that can inform policy-making, training programs, and practical applications in psychological counseling.

Methods. Desk research.

Results. Studies reviewed during the research demonstrated the effectiveness of various counseling techniques. For example, CBT was shown to be highly effective for anxiety and depression, while humanistic approaches were beneficial for enhancing self-esteem and personal growth. The research highlighted emerging trends such as the integration of technology in counseling (e.g., tele therapy, online counseling platforms) and the increasing importance of culturally sensitive practices. Challenges include addressing the stigma around mental health and ensuring access to counseling services for underserved populations. Best practices identified include ongoing professional development for counselors, the use of evidence-based interventions, and incorporating client feedback into the counseling process. Recommendations stress the need for culturally competent training and the utilization of digital tools to broaden access.

Conclusions. These results provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of the psychological counseling process, offering insights for practitioners, researchers, and policy-makers to improve the quality and accessibility of counseling services.

Keywords: psychological counseling, counseling techniques, social interventions.

EMOTIONAL HEALTH - THE BASIS OF GENERAL HEALTH

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Objectives. Increasing children's ability to plan and implement a healthy lifestyle using innovative expressive tools.

Methods. Coping strategies and self-care methods;

Results. Cultivating emotional well-being by starting with small daily actions, focusing energy on what can really make a difference;

- increasing the capacities of autonomy and independence in life;
- having increased control over every aspect of their lives: from feelings to thoughts, children can be better prepared and able to cope all the emotional sufferings and challenges of life.

Conclusions. Emotional intelligence helps children understand themselves and others, communicate and manage their feelings, regardless of their nature. These purchases will help them throughout their lives to develop and maintain relationships, both personally and professionally. Health is the level of functional and (or) metabolic efficiency of a living being. In humans, it is a person's general state of well-being in mind, body, and spirit, which usually means being free from disease, injury, or pain.

A comprehensive model of healthy living should address physical and mental training, nutrition and how to balance these with rest and physical relaxation.

Keywords: Connect with others, be physically active, live in the present moment, give to others, fundamental part of overall health.

SECTION C

Career Development and Guidance

Moderator: Mrs. Camelia IOANĂȘ

Argeș County Center for Resources and Educational Assistance

NAVIGATING YOUR CAREER PATH: A STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO SUCCESSFUL CAREER ORIENTATION & COACHING

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Abstract. Career orientation and career coaching are vital components of personal and professional development, offering individuals the guidance and tools necessary to navigate the complexities of today's job market. Career orientation helps individuals identify their interests, values, and strengths, providing a clear direction for career choices. Career coaching complements this by offering personalized advice, skill development, and strategies for overcoming challenges. Together, these processes foster informed decision-making, enhance employability, and build confidence. They also enable individuals to adapt to industry changes, expand their professional networks, and set strategic career goals. Ultimately, career orientation and coaching contribute to greater job satisfaction, personal fulfillment, and long-term career success.

Objectives. Evaluate strengths, interests, and values - self-reflection tools (e.g., personality tests, strength assessments), the importance of aligning career choices with personal values, practical tips for self-assessment, understanding career options - researching different industries and roles, how to conduct informational interviews or job shadowing, tools to help you explore (e.g., LinkedIn, career resources), defining short and long-term goals - setting SMART goals for your career, how to break down goals into actionable steps, aligning goals with personal growth and market trends.

Results. The audience will learn to: seek mentorship: gain personalized advice and guidance from experienced professionals, develop career resilience: build a growth mindset to handle challenges and setbacks effectively, regularly update career plans: revisit and adjust your career goals based on evolving personal and industry factors, take strategic risks: embrace calculated risks to open new opportunities and drive growth, focus on work-life integration: maintain a balance between professional success and personal well-being to prevent burnout, enhance learning agility: cultivate the ability to learn quickly and apply new skills in different contexts.

Conclusions. In conclusion, career orientation and career coaching are indispensable tools for individuals seeking to navigate their career paths with confidence and clarity. These processes not only provide essential guidance in aligning personal strengths and values with career goals but also help individuals make informed decisions and develop the skills needed to succeed in a dynamic job market. Career orientation ensures that individuals have a clear direction, while career coaching offers tailored support to overcome obstacles, build confidence, and enhance professional growth. By fostering adaptability, strategic goal-setting, and increased job satisfaction, career orientation and coaching significantly contribute to personal fulfillment and long-term success. Investing in these services is crucial for anyone seeking to achieve their full potential and thrive in their careers.

Keywords: orientation, coaching, tools, path, goals, values.

A CHANCE TO A BETTER LIFE

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Abstract. Inclusive education is an educational approach that ensures all students, regardless of their individual abilities, backgrounds, or learning needs, have equal access to quality education within mainstream schools. This approach values diversity and aims to foster a learning environment where every student feels respected, supported, and fully involved. Inclusive education focuses on adapting the educational system to meet the unique needs of each learner, rather than expecting students to adapt to a standard system.

Objectives. The paper goes through the key principles of inclusive education: equity and accessibility, diversity as a strength, individualized support, collaborative teaching and learning, social integration and participation, flexibility and adaptation and the challenges of implementing inclusive education: resource constraints, teacher training and support, class size and infrastructure, resistance to change.

Methods. Exercises, role-play.

Results. The participants will learn the benefits of inclusive education: improved academic outcomes, social and emotional growth, preparation for real-world diversity, enhanced teacher skills and innovation and some strategies for successful inclusive education: professional development, collaborative planning and teamwork, parent and community engagement, use of technology and assistive devices, creating an inclusive culture.

Conclusions. Inclusive education benefits everyone by fostering a supportive, dynamic, and empathetic learning community. As it continues to evolve, inclusive education has the potential to transform how we approach learning, making it a more enriching and equitable experience for all.

Keywords: inclusive education, learning, needs.

THE ROLE OF SCHOOL MEDIATORS, INCLUDING THE INCLUSION OF STUDENTS OF ROMA ETHNICITY

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Abstract. School mediators play a crucial role in bridging the gap between educational institutions, families, and communities, particularly for marginalized or underrepresented groups like the Roma community. Their primary function is to facilitate communication and foster inclusion by addressing both educational and socio-cultural barriers. School mediators play a pivotal role in fostering the inclusion of Roma students by acting as a bridge between the school and the Roma community, reducing barriers to education, and promoting cultural understanding. By providing support, promoting attendance, and advocating for inclusive policies, they help ensure that Roma students have better opportunities for academic success and social integration within the school system.

Objectives. The paper aims at presenting the advantages and the obstacles of being a school mediator, especially when working with students of Roma ethnicity.

Methods. Study cases.

Results. The paper explores the role of school mediators laying emphasis on the experience of the author. Also, the main focus lays on the inclusion of students of Roma ethnicity, since the author herself is of Roma descent.

Conclusions. School mediators working with Roma students face a variety of hardships due to the unique challenges associated with supporting one of Europe's most marginalized communities. The obstacles they encounter can be related to socio-economic issues, discrimination, lack of institutional support, and the deep-seated mistrust between the Roma community and formal educational systems.

Keywords: school mediator, Roma ethnicity, inclusion

TRUE-SELF-AS-GUIDE" AS SUCCESSFUL DECISION-MAKING STRATEGY FOR FURTHER STUDIES

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Abstract. There are gaps in the literature on further education as part of the career choice process, particularly in relation to secondary education. In the present study, we have processed empirical data on the decision to continue education among 13-15 year olds (grade VIII students in the Romanian education system). Specifically, we investigated the predictive value of four decision strategies in the realization of the preference for further education. In line with international trends, our results highlight an increase in the role of media popularity and a decrease in the role of parents and peers at this age. At the same time, they reveal the strong predictive value of a decision strategy based on true self as guide, which has been studied for the first time in both a national and international context in the secondary school age group.

Keywords: further education preference, success of further education decision, decision strategies

SECTION D

Workshops

Host: Mrs. Florina Laura FLORESCU

Argeş County Center for Resources and Educational Assistance

WISDOM OF THE BODY

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Abstract: In a world of super-fast technological progress, where we engage our mind with screens and gadgets, most of the days we forget that we have a body. This disconnection translates into feelings of loneliness, anxiety, depression and other forms of modern conditions.

By creating space to ask our bodies how they are, what they need, we can learn again the felt meaning of connection, from the inside.

The good news is that our own neurophysiology can support us to feel safer and connected.

Our Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) models how we live our lives. Beliefs, behaviours and body responses are intertwined. The ANS responds to our needs. The first step is to identify what those needs are: to survive or to connect?

When we are connected to ourselves from within and to the world around us, our neurophysiology will support us to grow and evolve. When we are in a defensive state, survival will be the only purpose and response of the ANS.

The workshop will go through some basic information from polyvagal theory and will have several frameworks in which we will apply tools for regulating the autonomic nervous system.

Objectives. The purpose of this workshop is to offer a basic education about the functioning of the autonomic nervous system, as well as some simple tools to create a deeper connection with the body.

Methods. Polyvagal Theory and Somatic Experiencing.

Results. Co-regulation and Education.

Conclusions. The body has an innate wisdom to heal. Learning how to access that wisdom can support us to become more alive, to thrive day by day in our lives rather than just survive. And since the most profound way we learn is through felt experience, exercises that support us in accessing the body wisdom are wonderful tools.

Keywords: Autonomic Nervous System, Polyvagal Theory, Self-Regulation.

WISDOM OF THE BODY

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Abstract: In a world of super-fast technological progress, where we engage our mind with screens and gadgets, most of the days we forget that we have a body. This disconnection translates into feelings of loneliness, anxiety, depression and other forms of modern conditions.

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Keywords: Autonomic Nervous System, Polyvagal Theory, Self-Regulation.

CULTIVATING OUR IMAGINATION

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Abstract. Cultivating imagination is a powerful process that enhances creativity, problem-solving, and emotional resilience. Imagination allows individuals to think beyond the immediate, visualize possibilities, and create new ideas. Imagination is key to discovering new possibilities. We first envision what we want, and then we take action to make it happen. Now, more than ever, in a world overflowing with stimuli, images, screens, problems, and demands, it's essential to free our minds, create space for ourselves, connect with our true selves, and cultivate the belief that we can achieve our dreams.

Objectives. In this workshop, we'll explore creative techniques to spark our imagination, clear our minds, and challenge our everyday limitations.

Methods. Mind Mapping, Brainstorming, Role-Playing or Improv Games.

Results. The aimed results are: Enhanced Creative Thinking, Greater Flexibility in Thought, Improved Problem-Solving Skills, Innovative Solutions, Confidence in Tackling Complex Issues, Increased Self-Expression, Comfort with Expressing Ideas Freely, Greater Emotional Awareness and Expression, Strengthened Collaboration and Teamwork, Synergy of Ideas, Boost in Confidence and Self-Belief, Increased Confidence in Creativity, Willingness to Take Risks, Development of New Skills, Storytelling and Communication, Visual Thinking, Metaphorical Thinking, Openness to New Ideas, Empathy and Perspective-Taking, Mental Breakthroughs, Emotional Catharsis, Stress Relief, Concrete Creative Outputs, Artworks, Stories, and Prototypes, New Ideas for Projects, Long-Term Impact on Personal Growth, Awakened Imaginative Potential.

Conclusions. The results of the workshop on cultivating imagination often include enhanced creative thinking, increased confidence in self-expression, better problem-solving abilities, and improved collaboration skills. Participants are more open to taking creative risks, thinking divergently, and applying imaginative thinking to everyday challenges, both professionally and personally. Tangible outputs like art, stories, and ideas, as well as increased personal growth and emotional well-being, are key outcomes of such a workshop.

Keywords: imagination, process, creativity.

THE LABYRINTH OF COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. The presentation is about communication as the process of exchanging information, thoughts or feelings between individuals or groups. It's a fundamental aspect of human interaction and occurs through various channels, including spoken and written words, gestures, body language, and even digital means like email or social media.

Objectives. In this workshop, we'll explore the communication styles. They refer to the ways in which people express themselves and interact with others. Each style has its own unique characteristics, strengths, and potential challenges. Understanding different communication styles can help improve relationships, reduce conflicts, and enhance personal and professional interactions.

Methods. Exercises, role-play.

Results. The participants will find their own communicational style and find out a lot of information about assertive communication (is generally most effective and promotes healthy relationships), passive communication (may be useful in a situation where it's better to listen rather than assert oneself) and aggressive communication (might be necessary in emergency situations where clear, direct action is needed quickly).

Conclusions. Effective communication requires practice, self-awareness, and often adapting one's style to suit the audience or situation. Developing these skills is valuable in both personal and professional settings. Developing flexibility to shift styles based on context, while maintaining respect and clarity, can help you become a more effective communicator in both personal and professional interactions. Practicing exercises regularly can significantly enhance communication skills, promoting a deeper understanding, empathy, and connection in both personal and professional settings.

Keywords: communication styles, assertive, passive, aggressive.

SECTION D

Projects

Moderator: Mrs. Camelia IOANĂȘ

Argeș County Center for Resources and Educational Assistance

FEEDBACKS FROM PRACTICAL TRAINING SESSIONS IN PORTUGAL

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(1,2,3,4) "Armand Călinescu" Technical College of Pitești.

Title of the project: "EUROPEAN SKILLS ACQUIRED DURING THE PRACTICAL TRAINING"

Project nr. 2023-1-RO01KA122-VET-000121012, in the fields of Education and Training, within Key Action 1 - KA 122 VET, ERASMUS+

Coordinator of the project: "Armand Călinescu" Technical College of Pitești

Source of the Grant: European Economic Area Grants;

Partners suport: GALEGA VENTURE

Partners host: Cozinha Com Arte

Objectives: Participants' personal and professional development to support future-oriented education and training, flexibility for the labour market, perfecting knowledge, skills and attitudes in the field of food service, enriching civic and cultural skills.

Other students in the school will be motivated to learn for their own selection in future projects. Employers prefer hiring our graduates due to their practical experience. This project makes our school become recognized locally and regionally as a high quality education and service provider.

Management details: Approved budget 43000 Euro. Time 12 months

Activities approved: VET

Results: 14 Europass Mobility documents, 14 Certificates of participation, 14 Language certificates, 14 Learning According + complements, 14 portfolios, the magazine *Practical Activities*, a FB page, the PR website, a panel with representative images.

Conclusions: 14 students completed 90 hours of training practice at a Portuguese restaurant, Cozinha Com Arte. We achieved learning outcomes for 7 students in the professional qualification of Gastronomy Technician and for 7 students in the professional qualification of Cook by carrying out practical training courses in a real working environment in European companies. The participants increased not only their professional training by acquiring learning outcomes in a EU country, but also their entrepreneurship and sense of initiative. They developed personally by enriching their social, civic, intercultural, linguistic skills, and increasing their self-esteem.

Keywords: professional, training.

IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL SKILLS THROUGH PARTICIPATION IN MOBILITY PROJECTS

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Programme Operator: National Agency for Community Programs in the Field of Vocational Education and Training (ANPCDEFP)

Project Promoter: Liceul Tehnologic Nr.1, Maracineni, Arges, Romania

Source of the Grant: EACEA through Erasmus+ Programme

Partners: GALEGA VENTURE, Lda, Montijo, Portugal; Jeronimo Martins Distribuição Alimentar (Pingo Doce), Lisboa, Portugal; İzmit Mesleki ve Teknik Anadolu Lisesi, İzmit, Turkey; KOCAELİ İLİ SÜS BİTKİLERİ ÜRETİCİLERİ BİRLİĞİ, Kocaeli, Turkey

Objectives: Development of the key skills of knowledge and execution of specific technologies of 21 students, future technicians in the fields of food industry, services and agriculture, Developing competencies for innovation and improving the quality of training of future graduates of 5 specialized teaching staff

Management details: Approved budget 65267 EURO/ Time 15 months (June 1, 2023 - August 31, 2024).

Activities approved: Job shadowing in Vocational education and training, Short-term learning mobility of VET learners

Results: *For the teachers:* The discovery of innovative tools for evaluating the theoretical and practical skills of high school/post-secondary school students; Improving the content of the curriculum of the disciplines. *For the students:* Application of microbiology concepts and hygiene rules in the food industry; Operation of machinery and equipment used in the food industry; Recognition and description of spaces at the level of the economic unit; Knowledge and use of resources at the level of the economic unit; Identifying the defining elements of marketing research; Select aggregates and agricultural installations used in plant protection depending on the work being performed; Coordinates the work formation that exploits portable devices and machines for treating crops by spraying; Coordinates the work formation that exploits portable devices and machines for treating crops by dusting.

Conclusions: The valorization of the European dimension that these training courses offered allowed the transfer of good practices from other education systems in the school space, in a manner adapted to the national specifics and for the benefit of our school unit. The European footprint of these training courses spread over the plans of our institution, in terms of the cross-border cooperation policy and the strategy of development and adaptation of the human resource to the particularity of the systems and education policies in the Member States. Through mobility projects, Liceul Tehnologic No. 1 promotes an education open to modernity and values the concrete potential of the students and teaching staff involved.

Keywords: Education, Grants, Projects.

EMPOWERING YOUNG EUROPEANS: BUILDING ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP THROUGH INTERNATIONAL EDUCATIONAL INITIATIVES

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Abstract. This article aims to present educational tools developed to enhance the awareness and skills of young Europeans in active citizenship. All indicators suggest that Romanians lack the ability, will, and capacity to recognize anti-social attitudes and behaviours, despite efforts by the educational system to promote active citizenship as a general concept. Considering that active citizenship behaviour is an extension of a society's beliefs and a vital factor for fostering positive attitudes, the project "*Citizens in Action*" — ERASMUS-JMO-2021-OFET-NET-101048265 seeks to create user-friendly educational tools for schools that are attractive to students, even from a young age. EU funding, previously limited to universities, is now available to schools through the *Jean Monnet in other fields of Education and Training: Networks* scheme, while maintaining a university research component.

Here is an overview of some didactic materials created within the project by teachers from an Italian university but designed for younger students in high school and elementary school: three training courses were developed: Course on gender equality, Course on European landscape, Course on Europe and European institutions.

Each project partner implemented local lessons based on the guidance received from Italian university teachers. These activities took place both during regular classes and outside school hours, including during the summer holiday. Project partners had the flexibility to organize the lessons according to their specific resources and students' availability. All materials and activities conducted in schools aimed to develop critical thinking and rethink attitudes.

Target group: 20 students from each partner school.

Project partners: schools from Romania, Italy, Latvia, and Greece.

Romanian partner: Micești Elementary School, Argeș County.

Approved activities: transnational meetings, intellectual outputs, multiplier events, and a student trip to Brussels in 2024.

Moreover, children developed strong principles aligned with European values through international experiences. Thus, 20 students from each partner school participated in an innovative mobility activity alongside students from four other European schools. This activity included a visit and interventions at the European Parliament, presentations of the research conducted by students and teachers involved in the project, and meetings with representatives of the European Parliament, in April 2024.

Conclusions. An active citizenship attitude is a necessary condition for achieving growth and social cohesion. In a world often on the brink of conflict, future leaders, whether of communities or nations, must be raised with positive attitudes and correct values.

Keywords: active citizenship, innovative educational tools, positive attitude, EU.

2023-1-RO01-KA120-ADU-000193208 ERASMUS+ THE ONSET OF AN ACCREDITATION TOWARDS SUCCESS

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Programme Operator: National Agency for Community Programs in the Field of Vocational Education and Training (ANPCDEFP)

Project Promoter: Argeș County Centre for Educational Resources and Assistance, Romania

Source of the Grant: EACEA through Erasmus+ Programme

Partners: MobilityFriends, Portugal,

Objectives: Developing the capacity of CJRAE Arges to produce changes in terms of modernization and international opening of the institution and adult education services in particular; Increasing the capacity of the staff to respond to the needs of adults with fewer opportunities, by the end of the accreditation period; Increasing the level of emancipation and self-esteem of the organization's trainers and adults/trainees through training and mobility activities, including international ones.

Duration: 01.02.2024 – 31.12.2027

Management details first year: Approved budget 40677 EURO/ Time 15 months (June 1, 2024 - August 31, 2025).

Activities approved first year: Job shadowing of staff, Short-term learning mobility of adult learners, training course of staff, Invited Expert.

Results: Herculano Daniel Andrade Texeira is providing ”*Involved Parents – Responsible Adults*” a 16 hours development course for teachers in Romania, and lecturing at the Self Development International Conference 2024.

START-UP, NEW GENERATION!
The power of together!
Erasmus+Accreditation 2021-2027

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Abstract(text:

The title of the project: Accreditation for an individual organization, 2020-1-RO01-KA120-SCH-095292

The objectives of the project:

O1: Digitalization of learning-teaching, studying by developing digital competences at least 40% of teachers

O2: Increasing the pupils interest in studying using ICT by minimizing with 20% of early leaving school

O3: Increasing the interest of SEN/ reduce opportunities of pupils in studying

O4: Developing linguistic competences for 40% of teachers

O5: Internationalisation of school by projects.

Operator de program: Agenția Națională pentru Programe Comunitare în Domeniul Educației și Formării Profesionale (ANPCDFP)

Source of the Grant: Erasmus+ grant

Objectives:

The purpose of this paper is to inform the public opinion and interested authorities about the financial and administrative evolution of the project. The objectives are: Public dissemination of the evolution state of the project.

Management details: Approved budget in 3 years of Erasmus+ accreditation is around 45.000 euro

Activities approved. Teachers training: course or jobshadowing. Mobility group of pupils.

Results: In 3 years of project 25 pupils were on mobility group of pupils in 3 schools from 3 countries: Bulgaria, Portugal, Turkey with 6 accompanying teachers and 8 teachers were on courses or jobshadowing.

Conclusions. Until now the project was a success. Every year the number of students was increasing and the number of teachers the same. For every student and every teacher the activities were a success because they were the beneficiary of develop their skills in ICT and foreign languages. The project will continue until 2027 – 2 years more – and the number of the teachers and pupils will increase.

Keywords: Education, Grants, Projects.

Parenting for happy children and successful adults – International Debate

Moderator: Mihaela LUNGU

GUESTS in DEBATE:

Ari POKKA (FINLAND), worldwide known principal and education policy maker, former: CEO of Finnish Education Institute, President of Finnish Association of Principals and International Confederation of Principals, Head of Development in First Finnish Senior High School in Doha Qatar.

Daniel Herculano ANDRADE TEXEIRA (PORTUGAL), specialist in human behavior and psychologist

Alin COMȘA (ROMANIA), lecturer at the Romanian Banking Institute – Bucharest – Training of Trainers department, specialist in coaching activity in management, sales, art and culture, NLP, communication, emotional intelligence, history or philosophy

Translators: Mihaela LUNGU, Camelia IOANĂȘ, Raluca Iulia ROȘULESCU

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